

**HISTORICAL STUDIES OF THE STUDY OF THE CULTURE OF THE EARLY
SAC TRIBES OF THE PRE-INDEPENDENCE PERIOD (1991–2026).**

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Abstract. This article systematically analyzes the stages of studying the culture of the first nomadic Sak-Massaget tribes of Central Asia in the historiography of the period of independence between 1991 and 2026, the achieved conceptual achievements and methodological innovations. Based on the results of the Chirik-Rabot archaeological expedition in recent years, new scientific concepts are analyzed about the existence of the Sak communities not just a herdsman's union, but also the first national state entities with monumental architecture, urban planning, and a complex structure. The article retrospectively reviews modern literature created on the basis of the principles of civilizational approach and digital archeology, and scientifically summarizes the specific features of the Sak material culture and fine art and their role in the ethno genesis of the peoples of the region.

Keywords: Sakas, Massagetae, historiography of the period of independence, Uzbek statehood, Chirik-Rabat expedition, civilizational approach, digital archaeology, ethno genesis.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence, the objective restoration of the historical past of the Uzbek and all Central Asian peoples, a deeper understanding of the roots of national statehood and the manifestation of identity rose to the level of state policy. In the context of these ideological and spiritual renewals, the study of the culture of the Sak-Massaget tribes is not just a collection of material evidence, but also serves as a criterion for reassessing the civilizational heritage of the peoples of the region on an international scale.

From this point of view, the historiography of the Independence period between 1991 and 2026 is considered a stage of absolutely new, fundamental turns and conceptual renewal in the study of the history of the early Sak tribes. Although the research conducted before 1991 created a huge experience and database for its time, they were formed under strong ideological pressures. The archeology and historiography of the Independence period freed science from politicized stereotypes. During this period, the Sak-Massaget communities began to be interpreted not as simply “wild nomads” or “herdsmen’s unions” living on the outskirts of settled civilizations, but as an independent civilization with a complex socio-political structure, monumental defensive architecture, and a unique philosophical worldview.

One of the greatest achievements of the modern Uzbek school of archeology in the last quarter of a century has been the systematic re-study of such monumental monuments as Chirik-rabot and Babish-mulla in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya River in a new methodological aspect. As a result of new research, theories have entered science that the Chirik-rabot monument was the

first monumental capital-fortress of the Sakan state. Thus, a systematic analysis of the evolution of the study of the material and spiritual culture of the Sak-Massages in the historiography of the period of independence, the achieved scientific results, and new methodological approaches is of great relevance today for the formation of a holistic theory of the ancient history of Central Asia that is objective, fair, and meets national interests.

Literature review.

The period of independence after 1991 opened the way for studying the history of the Sak-Massaget tribes, free from ideological stereotypes and based on new international standards. During this period, the history of the Saks was reassessed not just as a nomadic past, but as an integral part of the ethno genesis and history of statehood of the Uzbek people.

Academician A. Askarov proved that the Sak-Massagets were the oldest ethnic stratum that participated in the formation of the Uzbek people and considered them a pre-state stage of formation [1, 2]. Academician A. Sagdullayev, rejecting the old Soviet theory of permanent hostility between the Saks and the settled population, showed that they lived in conditions of mutually beneficial economic exchange and created structures resembling the first state [3, 4]. Academician R. Sulaymonov studied the military art and complex arcs of the Saks on the example of the Sogdian oasis of Yerkurgan, revealing their cooperation with the settled population [5, 6]. Academician E. Rtveldadze, on the basis of coins and written sources, investigated the history of the Saks' migration to the south [7, 8]. Archaeologist J. Kurbanov re-examined the Chirik-rabat monument as the capital of the Saks and discovered the magnificent pakhsa and mud-brick tombs there [9]. V. Yagodin studied the methods of the Saks on the Ustyurt plateau to adapt to the desert conditions, such as "pishan" and "aran" structures [10]. One of the scientists from Karakalpakstan, O. Shovdirbayev, analyzed the location of the Saks' fortifications and military strategy in relation to the landscape [11]. M. Reutov, studying ancient canals around Chirik-Rabat, proved that the agricultural and engineering potential of the Saka society was much higher than previously thought [12].

During the years of independence, significant scientific results were achieved in collaboration with Russian specialists. L. Yablonsky studied the ethnic appearance of Saka on the basis of bones found in Saka cemeteries and enriched this data with modern DNA analysis [13]. M. Itina created a chronological table of Saka monuments and confirmed that they were formed on the basis of local Bronze Age cultures [14]. B. Weinberg, comparing ancient and Achaemenid sources, drew a clear territorial map of the Saka tribes and showed their political independence through early coins and stamps [15].

Cooperation with Western European scientists introduced digital methods to the field. French scholar K. Rapin compared the defense system of Chirik-rabot with the military engineering of the Hellenistic world and assessed the Sakas as a cultural "bridge" on international trade routes [16]. M. Sier, using satellite imagery and Geographic Information Systems (GIS), created a digital landscape map of ancient riverbeds and irrigation networks [17]. This made it possible to clearly see how the Sakas adapted to natural changes.

Research Methodology.

The methodological basis of this study is the main principles of historical science of the period of independence: objectivity, historical consistency, and systematicity. In the process of the study, new scientific approaches, field research reports, and the results of international projects used

in the study of the material and spiritual culture of the Sak-Massaget tribes between 1991 and 2026 were analyzed.

Analysis and results.

Academician Ahmadali Askarov founded a new methodological school in the study of the history of the Sak-Massages during the years of independence. Based on archaeological and anthropological data, he scientifically substantiated the fact that the Sak-Massages were the oldest ethnic group that participated in the formation of the Uzbek people. He refuted the theory of hostility between nomadic and sedentary populations and proved their integration into a single cultural and economic territory [1].

The scientist assessed the union of the Sak-Massages tribes as a pre-state structural stage of the Uzbek statehood. In his opinion, the military-political system of governance of the Saks had a strong influence on the governance structure of the later medieval states [2].

Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, Professor Anatoly Sagdullaev successfully applied the civilizational approach and landscape archeology methods in the study of the union of the Sak-Massages tribes in the historiography of the years of independence. The scientist's research allowed for a new interpretation of the complex structure of the Saks society and their role in the formation of regional statehood.

A. Sagdullaev evaluates the Sak-Massages union not as a simple tribal union, but as a "form of the first state". According to the scientist, important signs of statehood were formed among the Saks. In particular: the hereditary nature of the power of tribal leaders and the separation of military-administrative functions, the existence of confederations that permanently maintained their political influence in a certain geographical area, etc. [3].

One of the central areas of A. Sagdullaev's research is the relationship of the Saks with settled agricultural oases. The scientist refutes the Soviet-era theory of "permanent hostility between nomads and settlers" and proves that they lived in conditions of mutually beneficial economic exchange. According to his conclusion, the Sakas were not only a supplier of livestock products, but also a force that ensured the defense of the oasis and distributed new cultural and technological elements [4].

Although the scientific work of Academician Rustam Sulaymanov is mainly focused on the Sogdian civilization, the relationship of the Sak-Massaget tribes with the settled oases, their military art and religious and ideological worldview play an important role in his research. He analyzed the military skill of the Sakas and their contribution to the development of Central Asian military art on the basis of archaeological materials. In particular, he evaluates the "complex bow" of the Sakas and the tactics of cavalry as one of the most advanced military achievements of antiquity. The scientist studied the structure of the Sakas bows, their ability to fire at long distances, and the subsequent use of this weapon in the Sogdian and Bactrian armies [5].

One of the most important conclusions of R. Sulaymanov is the issue of constant cultural and economic exchange between the nomadic Sakas and the settled agricultural oases. In the process of studying the Yerkurgan monument, the scientist noted the presence of Sak elements in the city's defense and material culture. He characterized the relations between the Sak-Massagets and the inhabitants of the Sogdian oasis as mutually beneficial cooperation, not hostility [6].

Academician Edward Rtveladze studied the geopolitical place of the Sak-Massaget tribes not only in the history of Central Asia, but also in the history of the entire Eastern world. His scientific approach was based on the analysis of written sources with numismatic data [7].

E. Rtveladze analyzed the relations of the Sakas with the Achaemenid Empire and the Greco-Bactrian state, showing them as one of the main factors in the development of regional security and international trade [8].

The work of archaeologist Jumanazar Kurbanov during the years of independence completely changed the perception of the Sak-Massagets as "only a nomadic population". He re-examined the Chirik-Rabat monument as the largest political and religious center of the Saks. During the excavations, magnificent tombs belonging to the Sak rulers and military aristocracy were discovered. The fact that these structures were built of pakhsa and mud brick proved the existence of a school of defensive and monumental architecture among the Saks [9]. The weapons, ceramics and jewelry found showed the uniqueness of the Chirik-Rabat culture and its inextricable connection with the ancient Khorezm civilization. Vadim Yagodin is the largest scientist who studied the culture of the Sak-Massaget tribes of the Aral Sea and the Ustyurt Plateau using landscape archaeology methods. The scientist discovered the unique stone-lined structures typical of the Ustyurt Plateau - huge stone barriers designed for hunting pishans and animals - arans, and shed light on their place in the Sak economy [10]. V. Yagodin studied the nomadic pastoral strategy of the Saks, their system of movement along wells and pastures, and showed that this population was perfectly adapted to the conditions of the steppe and plateau. scientific basis.

The contribution of Karakalpak researchers to the study of the history of the Sak-Massages is especially evident in the study of monuments along the ancient foothills of the South Aral Sea and the Syrdarya. These scientists continued the traditions founded by S.P. Tolstov during the years of independence, enriching the archaeology of the region with new finds.

Since the Aral Sea region was the main homeland of the Apasiaks, Tocharians and other Sak-Massages in antiquity, the research of Karakalpak archaeologists is of fundamental importance in studying the economic life and defense system of these tribes.

Archaeologist Omirbek Shovdirbaev has been conducting field research in the lower reaches of the Syrdarya and the Aral Sea region for many years. By studying the location of the Sak fortifications on the Syrdarya River and their connection with the natural landscape, he enriched the conclusions about the Saks' defensive strategy [11].

Mamatshafiq Reutov is an accomplished expert who has studied not only the Saks' fighting skills, but also their engineering and agricultural potential. Reutov has carefully studied the Chirik-rabat monument and the ancient canal system around it. He has provided evidence that the Saks built complex hydraulic structures and established agriculture in desert conditions [12]. His research has shown that the share of agriculture in the Sak-Massaget society was higher than previously thought, which served as the economic basis of the "oasis-steppe" relationship.

During the years of independence, cooperation between Russian and international scientists with Uzbek archaeologists has made it possible to analyze the history of the Sak-Massagets in a global context. As a result of this collaboration, many Soviet-era materials were re-examined based on modern laboratory analyses and new scientific conclusions were formed. The work of these scientists is of fundamental importance in determining the genetic roots, chronology and ethnic geography of the Saka-Massaget culture.

Leonid Yablonsky, not only an archaeologist, but also an accomplished anthropologist, studied the biological history of the Syr Darya Saka. He confirmed the “Europoid” appearance of the Saka by studying the skeletal remains found at the Tagisken and Uygarak monuments. He enriched the concept of the “Scythian-Saka world” connecting the Saka with the Scythians in the west and the Altai nomads in the east with modern DNA data [13]. He proved that the Saka culture is a complex synthesis of local and alien elements.

Maria Itina, as the most experienced representative of the Khorezm expedition, completed fundamental research linking the history of the Saka with the Bronze Age during the years of independence. She dated the Saka monuments in the lower reaches of the Syr Darya to the 10th century BC. He created a chronological structure starting from the 9th–8th centuries. Itina showed that the local Bronze Age tribes played a key role in the formation of the Saka culture, and supported the theory of local development with material evidence [14].

Bertha Weinberg is a major scholar who studied the territorial distribution of the Saka-Massaget tribes and their early state symbols. Comparing written sources and archaeological data, she drew a clear territorial map of the Apasiacs, Dakhs, and Massagets. B. Weinberg analyzed the first coins minted by the Saka-Massaget tribes and the stamps on them, revealing their political independence and foreign economic relations [15].

During the years of independence, cooperation with Western European specialists introduced high-tech methods and new theoretical perspectives into the historiography of the Saka-Massagets. The work of French scientists in the Aral Sea region made it possible to analyze the Chirik-Rabat culture in the context of world civilization.

During this period, archaeological excavations were not only about collecting artifacts, but also about digitally modeling the ancient ecological state of the area and the interaction of the population with the environment.

Claude Rapin (French National Center for Scientific Research – CNRS) in collaboration with the Institute of Art History and the Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan conducted many years of research at the Chirik-rabat monument.

K. Rapin studied the complex defensive walls and ditches of Chirik-rabat and compared them with the art of fortification construction of antiquity. He showed that the Sakas' defense system could compete with the military engineering of the Achaemenid and Hellenistic world [16]. The scientist interpreted the Sakas' culture as a cultural "bridge" between Central Asia and the Middle East, proving their active participation in international trade routes.

Michel Sierre used the methodology of landscape archaeology in studying the monuments of Chirik-rabat and the Syrdarya delta. Using satellite imagery and Geographic Information Systems, the scientist created a digital map of riverbeds and irrigation networks from the 1st millennium BC. This provides insight into how the Sakas used water resources in desert conditions.

Conclusion.

During the years of independence, the Uzbek schools of archaeology and history completely rejected the theory of irreconcilable hostility between nomads and sedentary populations, which had long dominated Soviet science and ancient texts. Instead, it was fully proven by material evidence that there was a mutually beneficial economic, military and cultural exchange between the Sak-Massaget world and the oasis civilizations, and that they lived integratedly in a single geopolitical area. As a result of the re-examination of such monumental monuments as Chirik-rabat and Babish-

mulla, it was revealed that in the middle of the 1st millennium BC, high monumental architecture, the art of building fortifications from pakhsa and mud brick, and a culture of irrigated agriculture based on a complex system of canals were formed in the Sakan society. This created a fundamental basis for assessing the Sak-Massaget tribal union as the earliest stage of the first state-like structure in the history of Uzbek national statehood.

Cooperation with Russian scientists paved the way for the transfer of the vast scientific conclusions accumulated during the Soviet era through modern laboratory tests. Craniological and the latest paleogenetic analyses confirmed the direct cultural and biological continuity of the Syrdarya Saks with the local Bronze Age tribes and confirmed their status as one of the oldest major ethnic groups that participated in the formation of the Uzbek people. At the same time, the study of the first Sak coins and tribal seals showed their independence in internal and external economic relations.

Cooperation with international Western European expeditions brought digital and geoarchaeological innovations. Using satellite imagery and Geographic Information Systems technologies, landscape-digital maps of ancient riverbeds and irrigation networks were created. This made it possible to model the adaptation strategies of Saka communities to the extreme desert climate, hydrological and ecological changes of the Aral Sea and the Ustyurt Plateau in a global context.

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